

EPR and Optical Study of Cu^{2+} Doped Potassium Hydrogen Bis Homophthalate

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Abstract

EPR study is carried out on Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate. Only one Cu^{2+} lattice site is observed. The site exhibits one set of four hyperfine lines in all directions. The g factor and hyperfine splitting are calculated from EPR spectra which are: $g_x = 2.0589 \pm 0.002$, $g_y = 2.0747 \pm 0.002$, $g_z = 2.1975 \pm 0.002$, $A_x = (74 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $A_y = (78 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $A_z = (161 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is found that Cu^{2+} enters the lattice interstitially. The ground state wave function of the Cu^{2+} ion in the lattice is determined from the spin Hamiltonian parameters obtained from EPR study. With the help of the optical absorption study, the nature of bonding in the complex is also discussed.

Keywords: EPR; Spin Hamiltonian; Absorption; Spectra; Angular variation; Rhombic symmetry

1. Introduction

EPR gives a detailed description of the ground state of paramagnetic ion and electric field symmetry produced by the ligands around the metal ion (Kripal et al., 2011; Kiczka et al., 2004; Koksal et al., 1999; Korkmaz et al., 1982; Kalkan and Koksal, 1997). Several studies of the cupric ion in octahedral or square planar coordination have been done. However, only few tetrahedrally coordinated cupric complexes have been studied as this ion coordinates mostly in octahedral configuration. Tetrahedral coordination configuration is especially interesting because the lack of inversion symmetry in such complexes leads to a mixing of the 3d and 4p orbitals on the cupric ion.

A theoretical study of CuCl_4^{2-} (Lohr and Lipscomb, 1963) indicates that the ground state contains about 8% 4p character and the excited states t_2 contain as large as 18% 4p character. The optical and magnetic investigation of CuCl_4^{2-} ion (Sharnoff, 1965; Sharnoff and Reimann, 1965; Ferguson, 1964) indicates that the t_2 orbitals contain about 12% 4p state admixture. In EPR study of copper (II) α - α' bromo dipyrromethene (Bates et al., 1962) the 4p admixture was found to be of the order

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of 20-30%. It is seen that, in these studies, although the g-values are not appreciably different from the typical g-values for distorted octahedral coordination, the copper nuclear hyperfine interaction parameters are markedly different. For a trigonally distorted tetrahedral environment of cupric ion in ZnO, the magnetic parameters are quite different than those in the tetragonally distorted octahedral cases (Deitz et al., 1962; Bates, 1962).

Benzoic acid derivatives and their salts have been studied in most cases because of the hydrogen bonding possibilities in the crystal structures. Analyses which fall into this category include potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate (benzene acetic acid, 2 carboxy-, monopotassium salt). O...O hydrogen bonds across centres of inversion is a feature of potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate. Considerable interest has been shown in benzene derivatives with ethanol amine side-chains, since many such compounds possess useful biological activities, being potent stimulants of adrenergic receptors (Sim and Sutton, 1974).

In the present study, the EPR and optical spectra of copper doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate are observed at room temperature. In this complex, the copper ion is in a distorted tetrahedral environment giving a new example of such uncommon complexes. The EPR parameters are quite similar to those typical of octahedral coordination. The results seem to suggest that the 4p admixture is about 34%. The superhyperfine (shf) interaction indicates a considerable amount of ligand character in the bonding orbitals.

2. Crystal Structure

The crystal structure of potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate, $[K(C_9H_7O_4)_2(H)]$, was reported by Gupta and Dubey (Gupta and Dubey, 1972). The potassium ion lies on the twofold axis (0, y, $\frac{1}{4}$) in the monoclinic unit cell with $a = 32.66(5)$, $b = 5.51(2)$, $c = 9.97(0)$ Å, $\beta = 95.9^\circ$, $Z = 4$ formula units of $[K(C_9H_7O_4)_2(H)]$; space group C2/c. There is a fourfold coordination around the potassium ion with potassium-oxygen distances ranging from 2.76 to 2.80 Å. The molecules are held together by van der Waals contacts, metal-oxygen ionic linkages and a short hydrogen bond of 2.59 Å between oxygen atoms belonging to carboxyl groups of adjacent homophthalic acid units. There is an ultrashort symmetrical hydrogen bond of 2.41 Å between two centrosymmetrically related oxygen atoms with the proton on a centre of symmetry.

3. Experimental

Single crystals of potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate doped with Cu^{2+} were grown from aqueous solution containing a trace of ethanol by mixing potassium hydroxide with homophthalic acid in stoichiometric amounts and slight admixture of (2%) copper sulphate at room temperature. After a few days, hexagonal thin plate like transparent crystals were formed (Gupta and Dubey, 1972). The morphology of the crystal together with the orientation of the crystal axes is shown in Fig. 1. Analysis: Calcd. for $[K(C_9H_7O_4)_2(H)]$: C, 54.27; H, 3.77; O, 32.16%. Found: C, 54.30; H, 3.78; O, 32.18%.

Fig. 1. Morphology and orientation of axes of the crystal.

The ESR spectra are recorded by using Varian E-1700 EPR spectrometer operating at X-band frequencies with 100 kHz modulation. A Varian flux meter with proton probe having 0.2 cubic centimeters of 0.25 molar solution of $GdCl_3$ in H_2O was used for magnetic field measurement along with a Hewlett-Packard frequency counter. For recording the EPR spectra, the crystal was rotated about a, b and c^* axes at an interval of 10° . c^* axis is perpendicular to a and b. The optical absorption spectra were recorded on Unicam-5625 spectrophotometer in the wavelength range 195-1100 nm at room temperature.

4. Results and Discussion

The spectra recorded at room temperature, when the magnetic field is along the c^* axis, are shown in **Fig. 2 (a)**. The spectra consist of one set of four hyperfine lines, which indicate that there is only one copper complex present in the lattice. Thus an interstitial site of Cu^{2+} ion is expected in the crystal. The lines of the above quartet has triplet structure clearly showing that the triplet is due to the interaction of unpaired Cu^{2+} electron and the two equivalent 1H ($I = 1/2$) nuclei. The angular dependence of the superhyperfine constant A^H for rotation of the crystal in all the three planes was investigated. The superhyperfine constant A^H varied from 20.0 to 25.0 G. EPR spectra recorded in ba and bc^* planes showed a large anisotropy in A and g values, however, the corresponding variation in c^*a plane is very small (Schonland, 1959; Chandramouli and Sastry, 1989). The spin Hamiltonian corresponding to rhombic symmetry is of the form

$$\mathcal{H} = \beta (g_z B_z S_z + g_x B_x S_x + g_y B_y S_y) + A_z I_z S_z + A_x I_x S_x + A_y I_y S_y \quad (1)$$

Computer simulation work has been done using the various parameters obtained from the EPR spectra of copper doped crystal using Schonland procedure (Schonland, 1959; Chandramouli and Sastry, 1989). The simulated spectrum using EasySpin (Pilbrow, 1969; Stoll and Schweiger, 2006; Stoll, 2003) and spin Hamiltonian parameters $g_x = 2.0589 \pm 0.002$, $g_y = 2.0747 \pm 0.002$, $g_z = 2.1975 \pm$

0.002, $A_x = (74 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $A_y = (78 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $A_z = (161 \pm 2) \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Frequency = 9.1 GHz) is given in **Fig. 2(b)**. The simulation was based upon numerical diagonalization of the entire $S = 1/2$, $I = 3/2$ energy matrix and the first derivative spectra. Lorentzian first derivative line shapes were used. The simulated spectrum is in good agreement with experimental one. The best-fit spin Hamiltonian parameters are given in **Table 1** which are similar to the values in other lattices (Sharnoff, 1965; Kokoszka, 1967). The parameter errors may be determined using statistical analysis (Misra and Subramanian, 1982).

Fig. 2. (a) EPR spectra of Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate for magnetic field along c^* -axis (Scan range: 4000G, Field set: 3200G, Time constant: 0.40 sec., Scan time: 4 min., Modulation frequency: 100 kHz., Modulation amplitude: 1x1G, Microwave frequency: 9.1 GHz, Receiver gain: $5 \times 10^2 \times 10$, Microwave power: 5 mW).
(b) Simulated EPR spectra of Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate along c^* -axis (Frequency = 9.1 GHz).

Table 1 Spin Hamiltonian parameters for Cu²⁺ ion site I in potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate single crystal

No.	Lattice	g _x	g _y	g _z	A _x	A _y	A _z	Ref.
					(10 ⁻⁴ cm ⁻¹)			
(1)	Cs ₂ ZnCl ₄ : Cu ²⁺	2.058	2.062	2.297	51± 5	46± 5	25± 4	(Sharnoff and Reimann, 1965)
		±0.004	±0.003	±0.002				
(2)	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂ ZnCl ₂ : Cu ²⁺	2.058	2.062	2.297	9± 4	9 ± 4	123± 4	(Sharnoff, 1965)
		±0.002	±0.002	±0.002				
(3)	ZnC ₂₈ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₆ : Cu ²⁺	2.0201	2.0900	2.1634	30± 2	40 ±2	154± 2	(Kripal et al., 2011)
		±0.002	± 0.002	± 0.002				
(4)	[K(C ₉ H ₇ O ₄) ₂ (H)]: Cu ²⁺	2.0589	2.0747	2.1975	74± 2	78 ±2	161± 2	*
		±0.002	± 0.002	± 0.002				

*present study

The angular variations of the spectra in all three planes ba, bc* and c*a have been plotted and are given in **Fig. 3 (a), (b)**. In the interest of locating the observed Cu²⁺ spectrum in potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate lattice, first we analyze the crystal structure. Considering the metal surroundings, it has four oxygen atoms in a flattened tetrahedral coordination. From consideration of the ionic size of Cu²⁺ (0.072 nm) and K⁺ (0.133 nm), it is reasonable to assume that copper enters the lattice interstitially. This is consistent with the fact that only one set of four hyperfine lines are observed in all three planes. This set corresponds to the ions, presently referred to as Cu²⁺ ions I.

It is possible to compare the direction cosines of various vectors calculated from the X-ray data (Gupta and Dubey, 1972) with those determined by EPR method. The essential features of potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate are illustrated in **Fig. 4**, which shows the [010] projection of the structure. The separation and direction cosines of various O-O vectors are given in **Table 2**. The direction cosines of O(1)-O(4) vector agree, within experimental errors, with those for the value of g_z of Cu (II) (**Table 2**). The Cu²⁺ ion sees tetrahedral oxygen coordination and consequently it will have D_{2d} site symmetry. The type of electric field produced by these surrounding oxygen atoms is obtained through the values of g as shown in **Table 1**. In potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate, O(1), O(3), O(4) and O'(4) with Cu-O distances 0.1589, 0.2382, 0.1590 and 0.1670 nm, respectively form a puckered square, O(2) and O'(3) may semi-coordinate (Krishna et al., 1992; Hathaway and Billing, 1970) at the top and bottom of the square with Cu-O distances 0.3613 and 0.3749 nm, respectively. These unequal metal ligand distances will have different binding strength and so the g-tensor is rhombic in this crystal.

Fig. 3. (a) Angular variation of g^2 for B in ba, bc* and c*a planes for Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate (Site I). **(b)** Angular variation of g^2A^2 for B in ba, bc* and c*a planes for Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate (Site I).

Table 2 Distances and direction cosines of various ligand-ligand vectors in potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate

Bond	Distance (Å)	Direction cosines		
		a	b	c*
O(1)-O(2)	2.210	±0.7066	±0.4615	±0.5362
O(1)-O(3)	3.348	±0.4522	±0.6686	±0.5901
O(1)-O(4)	3.146	±0.1068	±0.2744	±0.9556
O(2)-O(3)	5.477	±0.5616	±0.5936	±0.5762
O(2)-O(4)	4.913	±0.3865	±0.3804	±0.8401
O(3)-O(4)	2.189	±0.5716	±0.6711	±0.4720
g_x		-0.9946	0.1006	0.0267
g_y		-0.0973	-0.9897	0.1048
g_z		-0.1037	-0.2016	-0.9941

Fig. 4. The crystal structure viewed down [010].

Generally, the g-values reflect the property of the polyhedron in which the copper (II) ion is inserted and are dependent upon excited state energies, while A values are primarily influenced by the ground state, which in low symmetries are never pure d orbitals (Belford et al., 1977). Probably the rigid structure of the crystal imposes a higher degree of anisotropy in both g and A. The low value of copper hyperfine in the present system may be based on the finite admixture of the 'formal' $|xy\rangle$ ground state with the 4p state. The low value in case of cesium tetrachloro zincate (Cs_2ZnCl_4): Cu^{2+} and dichloro (1, 10-phenanthroline) zinc (II) ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{ZnCl}_2$): Cu^{2+} (Sharnoff, 1965; Kokoszka et al., 1967; Rivoal and Briat, 1974) has been accounted for based on the finite admixture of the 'formal' $|xy\rangle$ ground state with 4p state.

4.1. Optical spectrum

The room temperature optical absorption spectrum of Cu^{2+} doped potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate single crystal, in the wavelength range 195-1100 nm is exhibited in **Fig. 5 (a), (b)**. There are three bands occurring at $\nu_1 = 9321 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_2 = 15567 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\nu_3 = 20582 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, in 325-1100 nm range and four bands in the ultraviolet (UV) range, most of which are weak in intensity, occurring at $\nu_4 = 27463 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_5 = 32218 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_6 = 37090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_7 = 49904 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) Room temperature absorption spectrum in the wavelength range 195-325 nm. **(b)** Room temperature absorption spectrum in the wavelength range 325-1100 nm.

From the nature of absorption spectrum, the absorption band at ν_1 can be regarded as the d-d transition band between the ground state $|xy\rangle$ and the excited state $|x^2 - y^2\rangle$. The band at ν_2 may be regarded as the d-d transition band between the ground state $|xy\rangle$ and the excited state $|xz, yz\rangle$. The other band observed at ν_3 is assigned as $|3z^2 - r^2\rangle \leftrightarrow |xy\rangle$ transition band.

The four observed absorption bands in the UV range, occurring at $\nu_4 = 27463 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_5 = 32218 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_6 = 37090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_7 = 49904 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, are probably, the charge-transfer transition bands, because they arise from higher-lying energy levels. The present results can be compared with those for CuCl_4^{2-} complex (Desjardins et al., 1983). Using the results for CuCl_4^{2-} the four transition $1a_2 \leftrightarrow 5b_2$, $5e_2 \leftrightarrow 5b_2$, $3e \leftrightarrow 5b_2$, $2a_1 \leftrightarrow 5b_2$ correspond to the observed frequencies $\nu_4 = 27463 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_5 = 32218 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_6 = 37090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu_7 = 49904 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In regular T_d symmetry the 2D term of the ion splits into a low-lying doublet (E) and a high-lying triplet (T_2) with splitting equal to

$$D_t = 20q F_4(R)/27 \quad (2)$$

where D_t is tetrahedral cubic splitting, q is the effective charge of ligand in units of elementary charge, R is distance of the ligand from the central metal ion and $F_4(R)$ is the fourth-order radial integral of the central field (Schlafer and Gliemann, 1969). On the assumption of small radial extension of the unpaired electron wave function,

$$F_4(R) = \langle r^4 \rangle / R^5 \quad (3)$$

with $\langle r^4 \rangle$ the mean-fourth-power radii of the 3d orbital.

Taking $\langle r^4 \rangle = 0.19555 \text{ \AA}^5$ (Abragam and Bleaney, 1970),

$$D_t = 16885.488q / R^5 \quad (4)$$

where D_t is in cm^{-1} and R in angstroms. For $R = 2 \text{ \AA}$ and $D_t \approx 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $q = 5.7e$. Thus, value of the ligand effective charge provides good agreement between theory and experiment, and it will be used here.

The tetragonally (D_{2d}) distorted four coordinated complex is shown in **Fig. 6**. The perturbation parameter is given by the angle β between the z axis of the complex and the Cu-ligand vector.

Fig. 6. Tetragonal (D_{2d}), rhombic (C_{2v}) and trigonal (C_{3v}) distortions in a tetrahedron ($\beta=54.74^\circ$, $\beta'=109.48^\circ$, $\phi=90^\circ$, $h=0.707 \text{ \AA}$, and $R=0.612 \text{ \AA}$ for T_d symmetry).

According to the deformation angle, a regular tetrahedron ($\beta_T = 54.74^\circ$), an elongated tetrahedron ($\beta < \beta_T$), a flattened tetrahedron ($\beta > \beta_T$), or a square-planar complex for $\beta = 90^\circ$ is obtained. Determining the matrix element of the crystal field perturbation in D_{2d} symmetry and solving the secular equation of the 2nd degree, the energies of the 3d orbitals are found as (Hoffmann and Goslar, 1982)

$$\begin{aligned}
 E |3z^2 - r^2\rangle &= 2D_s (3\cos^2\beta - 1) + \frac{27}{140}D_t (35\cos^4\beta - 30\cos^2\beta + 3) \\
 E |xy\rangle &= -2D_s (3\cos^2\beta - 1) + \frac{9}{140}D_t (35\cos^4\beta - 50\cos^2\beta + 19) \\
 E |x^2 - y^2\rangle &= -2D_s (3\cos^2\beta - 1) + \frac{9}{35}D_t (5\cos^2\beta - 4) \\
 E |xz, yz\rangle &= D_s (3\cos^2\beta - 1) - \frac{9}{70}D_t (35\cos^4\beta - 30\cos^2\beta + 3) \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } D_s = 9539.055q/R^3 \tag{6}$$

and D_s is in cm^{-1} if R is in angstrom. D_s is a tetrahedron crystal field parameter and is related with D_t as

$$D_s (\text{cm}^{-1}) = 0.565932 R^2 D_t \tag{7}$$

For all known Cu-ligand separation R , in tetrahedral complexes, D_s exceeds D_t .

It has been shown (Hoffmann and Goslar, 1982) that in compressed tetrahedron $|xy\rangle$ is the ground state if $\beta = 54.74-90^\circ$. When the tetrahedron undergoes elongation ($\beta = 0-45^\circ$) the ground state is $|3z^2 - r^2\rangle$, and splitting is greater than in the flattened tetrahedron. From $\beta = 45$ to 54.74° the ground state is degenerate, $|xz, yz\rangle$. This degeneracy is removed by spin-orbit coupling.

The orbital splitting with respect to ground state is shown in **Fig. 7** for the above cases. A greater elongation of the tetrahedron should not be expected to occur because of increasing ligand-ligand repulsion. The experimental orbital splitting energies have been shown by circles in Fig. 7 and thus β comes out to be 75° with $|xy\rangle$ as the ground state.

Fig. 7. The plot of orbital splitting with respect to ground state (Cu-ligand separation = 2.10Å and $q = 6.2e$ are taken).

Both the experimental and calculated energies together with D_s and D_t of the d-d transition bands are given in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Experimental and calculated energies together with D_s and D_t of the d-d transition bands.

Transition	Band position (cm ⁻¹)		D_s	D_t
	Observed	Calculated		
$d_{xy} \leftrightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$	9321	8750	6397	2563
$d_{xy} \leftrightarrow d_{xz, yz}$	15567	15849		
$d_{xy} \leftrightarrow d_{3z^2-r^2}$	20582	22513		

A tetragonally flattened tetrahedron occurs with $\beta \approx 60^\circ$ in blue protein (Solomon, et al., 1980), with $\beta \approx 60^\circ$ in the series of pyrrole-2-carboxaldehyde Schiff base Cu (II) complex (Yokoi and Addison, 1977) and with $\beta \approx 70^\circ$ in the series of bis (salicylaldiminato) Cu (II) complexes (Bertini et al., 1980). A tetragonally flattened tetrahedron also occurs with $\beta \approx 75^\circ$ in bis-(5, 5'diethylbarbiturato) bis picoline Zn (II) single crystal doped with Cu^{2+} ion Kripal et al., 2011). A tetragonally elongated tetrahedron with ground state $|3z^2 - r^2\rangle$ has been proved by EPR in $\text{CaWO}_4: \text{Cu}^{2+}$ (Lynch and Sayer, 1974). A similar result of CuCl_4^{2-} tetrahedron subject to D_{2d} deformation has been given (Smith, 1970) on the assumption of the covalency of σ and π bonding. The reasonably large deviation of theoretical transition energies from experimental values may be due to contributions of additional factors not considered in theoretical calculations. These important contributions are expected from metal-ligand as well as ligand-ligand repulsion, overlap-induced configuration interaction and many-electron reorganization effects (Desjardins et al., 1983).

4.2. Analysis of EPR data

Taking $|xy\rangle$ as the ground state in D_{2d} , flattened tetrahedral Cu (II) complex the crystal field can admix the state $4p_z$ of the same symmetry. Similar effects of hybridization occur for the states $|xz\rangle$, $|yz\rangle$ and $4p_x, 4p_y$. Thus, the wave functions may be written as (Hoffmann and Goslar, 1982)

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi(B_2) &= \alpha |xy\rangle + \eta p_z \\ \Phi(B_1) &= |x^2 - y^2\rangle \\ \Phi(E) &= \gamma |xz, yz\rangle + \zeta p_{x,y} \\ \Phi(A_1) &= \delta |3z^2 - r^2\rangle + \delta_1 S\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

Hence, neglecting second-order terms in η and ζ , the spin Hamiltonian parameters become

$$\begin{aligned}g_{\parallel} &= 2.0023 - 8\alpha^2\lambda_d/E_1, \\ g_{\perp} &= 2.0023 - 2(\alpha^2\gamma^2\lambda_d - \alpha\gamma\zeta^2\lambda_p)/E_2 \\ A_{\parallel} &= P_d [-\kappa\alpha^2 - \frac{4}{7}\alpha^2 + (g_{\parallel} - 2) + \frac{3}{7}(g_{\perp} - 2)] + P_p\eta^2 (-\kappa + \frac{4}{5}), \\ A_{\perp} &= P_d [-\kappa\alpha^2 + \frac{2}{7}\alpha^2 + \frac{11}{14}(g_{\perp} - 2)] + P_p\eta^2 (-\kappa - \frac{2}{5}),\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

where E_1 = energy separation between $|xy\rangle$ and $|x^2 - y^2\rangle$ states

E_2 = energy separation between $|xy\rangle$ and $|xz, yz\rangle$ states

$\lambda_d = -829 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_p = -925 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are free-ion spin-orbit coupling constants for 3d and 4p orbitals, respectively. $P_d = 0.0360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $P_p = 0.0402 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are the copper-ion dipolar hyperfine structure parameters for 3d and 4p orbitals, and κ is the Fermi contact parameter. An admixture of B_2 and E states does not affect g_{\parallel} but slightly lowers g_{\perp} and A_{\perp} . The $4p_z$ mixing strongly affects hyperfine structure splitting A_{\parallel} .

In the present case, there are five unknown coefficients, the four MO coefficients and the Fermi contact parameter. Two MO coefficients α^2 , η^2 and κ , the Fermi contact parameter are estimated using equations for g_{\parallel} , A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} . The other two MO coefficients γ^2 and ζ^2 may be evaluated from equation for g_{\perp} by fitting the MO coefficients using a least-square technique to $M = (g_{\perp,cal}/g_{\perp,obs} - 1)^2$ with the condition that the best fit MO coefficients minimize the value of M. Here obs. and cal. indicate the observed and calculated values, respectively. The MO coefficients α^2 , η^2 , γ^2 , ζ^2 and κ , so determined using computer are 0.45, 0.34, 0.98, 0.0001 and 0.21, respectively. The coefficients γ^2 and ζ^2 are characterized by the value $M = 1.65 \times 10^{-4}$.

α^2 indicates that the σ -bonding is strongly covalent in nature. Since it shows that the bond is delocalized over both the Cu (II) and ligand orbitals. If $\alpha^2 = 1$, the bond will be completely ionic. If the overlap integral is vanishingly small and $\alpha^2 = 0.5$, the bond would be completely covalent. The smaller the value of α^2 the greater the covalent nature of the bond. On the other hand, there is no in-plane covalent π bonding in the complex. The present value of γ^2 , being very close to unity ($\gamma^2 = 0.98$) indicates the out-of-plane covalent π bonding is quite small. As the values of α^2 and β^2 decrease, the bonds become more covalent (McGarvey, 1966). Thus, the nature of bonding with the ligands along the axis is expected to be mostly ionic. The parameter κ , the contact term, is a measure of the polarization produced by the uneven distribution of d-electron density of the inner core s-electrons and it has been suggested (Van Vleck, 1932) that for the 3d transition metal ions $\kappa \approx 0.3$. From the value of η^2 , it is found that the ground state metal orbital contains about 34% 4p-state admixture.

5. Conclusion

EPR together with optical absorption study of potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate single crystal doped with Cu^{2+} has been done. The principal g and A parameters are evaluated from EPR spectra and are fitted to rhombic symmetry spin Hamiltonian. The angular variation plot showed that the Cu^{2+} ion enters the lattice interstitially. The ground state wave function for Cu^{2+} in the lattice is constructed which is found to contain about 34% 4p-state admixture. The optical absorption spectrum has been explained well in terms of a D_{2d} symmetry in the Cu^{2+} complex. The estimated MO coefficients indicate that for the Cu^{2+} complex in potassium hydrogen bis homophthalate lattice, the bonding between the Cu^{2+} ion and the oxygen ligands is strongly covalent while the bonding between the Cu^{2+} ion and its axial ligands is mostly ionic.

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